

Adsorptive removal of Reactive Blue 160 from aqueous solutions using polyaniline modified alumina nano composites

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Abstract : In this work, we are reporting the effect of modification of alumina (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles with polyaniline (PANI) on its adsorption capacity for the removal of dyes in the textile wastewater. The polyaniline-alumina (PANI-AL) composites used for this study were prepared in a simple adsorption method in which PANI was made to adsorb on the surface of commercial alumina from the solution of dimethylformamide. The adsorption potential of PANI-AL composites were evaluated for the removal of Reactive Blue 160 (RB 160) from aqueous solution. The influence of various experimental parameters such as contact time, adsorbent dose, dye concentration, pH and temperature on dye removal efficiency was also investigated. The composites show excellent adsorption capacity and reproducibility for RB 160. The optimum dosage of the composites for the removal of dye was 1 g L⁻¹ for dye solution at pH 3 in room temperature. Adsorption data was validated with Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. The results show that PANI-AL is a good adsorbent for removal of organic dyes from textile effluent.

Keywords : Adsorption, alumina, polyaniline, surface modification, Reactive Blue 160.

Introduction

Water pollution due to the industrial effluents is an important problem in many growing countries. Water sources such as lakes, river, streams and pond are contaminated by untreated effluents discharged by industries. These contaminants cause serious environmental and health issues. Among the most industries, water pollution due to the textile dyeing industries are alarmingly high. It is estimated that 10–15% of dyes produced annually are discharged into the water. These dye molecules are also non biodegradable and stable to sunlight and most oxidizing agents due to their complex structure¹. Further, dyes used for dyeing of cotton fabrics contains one or more azo groups to produce different colours. These azo dyes under anaerobic condition are reduced to highly toxic and carcinogenic aryl amines. Due to the mutagenic and non biodegradable nature of organic dyes, treatment and removal of residual dyes in the effluent should be done before it was discharged into the natural water sources. These effluents can be treated in physical and chemical

methods. However physical effluent treatment methods are comparatively greener since they did not involve any additional chemicals. In the physical wastewater treatment method, adsorption is extensively studied for the removal of textile dyes because it is a cleaner, more efficient and cheaper technology². Metal oxides with have been used as adsorbents for the removal of several pollutants in water^{3,4}. Among them, alumina (Al₂O₃) has been recognized as an efficient inorganic adsorbent due to its excellent physical-chemical properties and low toxicity⁵. In several studies surface of the alumina has been modified with surfactants^{6,7} and other organic compounds to increase its adsorption efficiency. Similarly, polyaniline (PANI) a conjugated polymer was used adsorb many sulphonated dyes from the effluent⁸. PANI was also used to modify the surface of metal oxide and non-metal oxide adsorbents. PANI modified alumina (PANI-AL) was reported to have high adsorption capacity for the removal of heavy metals in water. However the efficiency of PANI-AL composite for removal of organic dyes was not much

studied. Hence, in the present work, we have studied the application polyaniline-alumina composites (PANI-AL) for the removal of organic dye RB 160 from aqueous solution.

Synthesis of polyaniline :

Polyaniline was prepared in a free radical oxidation method in which aniline (0.2 M) dissolved in 0.2 M HCl was oxidized with ammonium peroxydisulphate (5.71 g, 25 mmol) solution. In the synthesis, ammonium peroxydisulphate solution was dropwise added to the solution of aniline hydrochloride solution in a beaker maintained at 0–2 °C in an ice bath. After the completion of the addition of oxidant the mixture was stirred for 10 h to facilitate the polymerisation.

Preparation of PANI-AL composites :

In the synthesis of PANI-AL composites, 1 g of Al_2O_3 powder was added to 100 ml of 0.2% polyaniline-dimethyl formamide (DMF) solution, the mixture was stirred for 24 h. Then the solid was filtered off, washed with water and dry in a hot air oven at 80 °C for 24 h.

Results and discussion

Effect of contact time :

The effect of contact time on the adsorption of RB 160 on PANI-AL and unmodified Al_2O_3 is given in the Fig. 1. Adsorption of RB 160 on both adsorbents are steady for initial 10 min and slow decolourisation was observed in later stages. However, there is no significant

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on decolourisation (dye concentration = 100 mg L⁻¹, adsorbent dosage = 1 g L⁻¹, pH = 3).

decolourisation after 3 h from the start of adsorption process. This shows that equilibrium can be assumed to be achieved after 3 h (180 min) due to the saturation of the

active sites. The steady adsorption of dye molecules in the initial stages was due to the availability of large number of surface sites and after a lapse of time, most sites are occupied by the dye molecules and the remaining surface sites are difficult to be occupied because of repulsion between the adsorbed dye on PANI-AL and dye molecules in the solution⁹. The studies shows that the PANI-AL has better colour removal ability than the unmodified Al_2O_3 .

Effect of initial pH :

The influence of initial pH on RB 160 removal was studied by changing the pH of the dye solution from 3 to 12. The concentration of dye solution for the study was 100 mg L⁻¹ and the dosage of adsorbent was 1 g L⁻¹, and the results were given in the Fig. 2. Maximum dye removal was observed when the pH of the solution is 3 and on the increase of pH, the dye removal efficiency of the

Fig. 2. Effect of initial pH of the dye solution on decolourisation.

adsorbent decreases. This is because the change of pH of the dye solution alter the surface charge on the adsorbent. When the pH of the solution was below the point of zero charge (pzc) of the PANI-AL composites, the adsorbent surface acquires positive charge due to protonation and similarly the material acquires negative charge when pH was above pzc^{10,11}. Thus as the pH decreased, more positively charged surface was available for adsorption of more dye molecules.

Effect of initial concentration of dye and dosage of adsorbent :

The effect of the initial concentration of RB 160 solu-

tion non the removal efficiency of PANI-AL composites has been studied by varying the initial dye concentrations of RB 160 from 25 to 125 mg L⁻¹ at 30 °C. Fig. 3a shows that the percentage dye removal decreases gradually on increase of dye concentration above 75 mg L⁻¹ due to saturation of adsorption sites in PANI-AL composites¹². Further for dye concentration above 100 mg L⁻¹, the increase of adsorbent dosage increases the percentage of dye removal. Fig. 3b shows that 100 mg L⁻¹ dye could be completely decolourised by PANI-AL composites when its dosage was above 2 g L⁻¹. The increase in decolourisation rate at higher dosage was due to increase of surface area available for adsorption¹³.

Fig. 3. (a) Effect of initial dye concentration on RB 160 at initial pH 3 and adsorbent dosage 1 g L⁻¹. (b) Effect of dosage of adsorbent on removal of 100 mg L⁻¹ RB 160 dye.

Kinetic studies :

The adsorption of RB 160 onto PANI-AL composites was fitted to both pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order models (Fig. 4). The best-fit model was determined based on the linear regression correlation coefficient values. The results shows that the adsorption of dye on PANI-AL composites follows pseudo-second order kinetics with R^2 values lies between 0.99–1.

Thermodynamics studies :

Adsorption data at room temperature was fitted to both Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption models (Fig. 5). However, the Langmuir adsorption isotherm model ($R^2 = 0.999$) fits well than the Freundlich model ($R^2 = 0.961$). This shows that dyes form a monolayer over the adsorbent surface. The K_f value for the adsorption was 2.037. This high value indicates adsorbent has high affinity for the dye molecule¹⁴, and the value of $1/n_f$ (0.24) lies between 0 and 1 indicating favorable adsorption.

Fig. 4. (a) Pseudo-first order and (b) pseudo-second order adsorption kinetic plots for the adsorption of RB 160 on PANI-AL composites.

Fig. 5. (a) Langmuir and (b) Freundlich adsorption isotherm for adsorption of RB 160 on PANI-AL.

Conclusion

PANI-AL composites has been prepared successfully and its adsorption efficiency was evaluated from the decolourisation of RB 160 dye in aqueous solution. The kinetics of dye adsorption fits well to the pseudo-second order model. The fit of the Langmuir model in the present system shows the formation of a monolayer covering of the adsorbate at the outer surface of the adsorbent. The PANI-AL sorbent is easy to synthesize, and also it is possible to regenerate or activate the adsorbent by washing with 1 molar NaOH in order to reuse them for successive removal processes. Hence the PANI-AL composites will be a good material for removal of anionic dyes like RB 160 from textile effluents.

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